

Investigating the Impacts of Information and Communication Technology Systems in Conducting Population Census in Tanzania: A Case of National Bureau of Statistics

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Abstract:

This study investigated Impacts of ICT system in conducting population census in Tanzania. This study employed a quantitative research approach and a case study research design, the targeted population was 583 in which the sample size of 237 was obtained under simple random sampling and purposive sampling techniques. Data was collected through questionnaires and was analyzed through SPSS V. 26. The findings show that overall performance of the ICT system in population census was 62.8%. Through multiple regression analysis a more specific function of ICT system on population census were determined, it was shown that the use of ICT system in the collection of the socio-demographic information had $\beta = .138$, $p < .001$), also on the Data Development and Dissemination it was shown that $\beta = .061$, $p < .003$, lastly on the Monitoring and Evaluation provides that $\beta = .539$, $p < .000$. Therefore, it was concluded that there was a positive and significant relationship between the use ICT system and the performance of the population census in Tanzania. The study examined the roles of effective census information on national development in which it was revealed that census information facilitates the allocation of the government resources, determine the size of population the country has in order to forecast if the amount of money that is provided by the government for development effort is sufficient. The study recommends the provision of effective measures to ensure the security and privacy of the information collected so that it cannot be mismanaged and misappropriated.

Keywords: *Population Census, National Bureau of Statistics, ICT.*

Introduction

The adoption and use of ICT systems in the national population census were made possible by the developments on desire to conduct some more effective censuses as sources of crucial information (United Nations Statistics Division, 2010). In the adoption of the ICT system the United States, the Bureau of Statistics considers

itself as a digital pioneer by making the US one of the nations which successfully replaced the long form used in decennial censuses with ICT-based data-gathering methods for its population census in 2000 (Alexander, 2020). Also, ICT systems were adopted and used in Brazil's census, where portable devices were used by enumerators to find homes on the ground, and the ability to submit census responses online

(Dekker, 2011). In the UK all census information are now scanned, kept electronically eliminating the need for physical archives, without the use of massive databases maintained on a computer, the record linkage required to conduct an administrative census would not be possible if there was no adoption and application of ICT (Beynon, 2009). In the past, when ICT was not widely utilized, tabulations of tasks like censuses were done manually, and difficult questions weren't addressed since their analysis was impossible (Biljecki et al., 2016). The advent of electronic tabulations and analysis completely altered this situation. Modern computers have sparked a second revolution that has shifted the bottlenecks to the data-transfer stages, when the written records are converted for computer use and when the tabulated results are to be printed books. This is because complex tabulations can now be made quickly thanks to modern computers (Waite, 2010).

The NBS ICT policy, which the NBS aims to support the development plan 2016/2017 - 2020/2021, was created in 2017 after a review of the NBS policy to oversee the development of ICT in the institution in response to these difficulties. Another census in Tanzania was conducted in 2022, with automation and ICT use reflecting Tanzania's growth goals of 2030 and Vision 2025. Thus, the implementation of the Statistics Act 2019 and the NBS ICT policies 2017 encouraged the application of ICT in the process of enumeration of people which has taken place in Tanzania on 23 August 2022 because the national Bureau of statistics NBS says that the application of new ICT systems such as mobile Geographical Information System Technologies (GIS) and other systems assures the country of accurate and timely data during the 2022 population census and Housing census PHC, the present study assess the impacts of ICT system in conduct of population census in Tanzania with the following objectives.

- To examine the use of ICT in the collection of socio-demographic information on the census in Tanzania

- To identify the effects of ICT on the data development and dissemination of information during the census
- to examine the roles of ICT systems in monitoring and evaluation of the population census in Tanzania.

Materials and Methods

Location of the Study

The study was conducted at the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) in Dodoma because this organization is responsible for planning, designing, implementing, and evaluating the ICT system that was used to collect population data for the census in 2022. As a result, the staff members there are familiar with the impact of ICT on population counts.

Data Collection Procedure

The researcher selected 237 respondents from NBS Officials, ICT Supervisors, Census Clerks, and Content Supervisor, the study employed questionnaires to obtain the information necessary for this study such as age, gender, level of education and experience with ICT. Other information obtained were those related to contribution of ICT in collection of demographic information, the effects of ICT on the data development and dissemination and role of effective census information on national development programs.

Data Analysis

Data collected through questionnaire were coded through Statistics Package for Social Science (SPSS V20), in the analysis process the researcher employed different process such as demographic characteristics presented in Table. Also, the researcher employed descriptive statistics as well as multiple regression analysis to establish the relationship between research variables.

Results and Discussion

Table 1, shows that 55.5% of the respondents aged 26 – 35 years, 16.3% of the respondents

aged 45 – 50 years, 12.4% of the respondents had 18 – 25 years, while 8.1% of the respondents had 51years and only 7.7% of the respondents aged 36 – 45 years. On the gender of the respondents, Table, 2 shows that 53.6% of the respondents were male, while 46.4% of the respondents were females. On the level of education of the respondents, Table 4.1 shows that 53.1% of the respondents had bachelor's degrees, also 28.7% of the respondents had a diploma-level education and 18.25 of the respondents had master's degrees. On the

experience with ICT system Table 2 shows that 26.8% of the respondents had experience below 1 year, 36.4% of the respondents had between 1 – 3 years' experience with ICT systems, 29.2% of the respondents had 7 years' experience and above, while 7.7% of the respondents had the experience of 4 – 6 years. Analysis of the demographic information of the respondents who participated in this study was very important since it ascertain the ability of the respondent to understand the questions being asked (Dekker, 2011).

Table 1 Demographic Information of the Respondents

Character	Category	Frequency	Per cent
Age	18 – 25 years	26	12.4
	26 – 35 years	116	55.5
	36 – 45 years	16	7.7
	45 – 50 years	34	16.3
	50+ years	17	8.1
Gender	Male	112	53.6
	Female	97	46.4
Level	Diploma education	60	28.7
	Degree	111	53.1
	Masters	38	18.2
Experience with ICT systems	Below 1 year	56	26.8
	1 – 3 years	76	36.4
	4 – 6 years	16	7.7
	7 years and above	61	29.2

Impacts of use of ICT Systems on Performance of Population Census

This section presents the existing relationship between the research variables namely the independent variables and the dependent variable. The independent variable of this study was mainly three CSD (Collection of Social Demographic Data), DD (Development and Dissemination) and ME (Monitoring and Evaluation), while the dependent variable was PC (Performance of Census). To establish the existing relationship between these variables' statistical tests such as descriptive statistics, and inferential statistics, multiple regression analysis was employed by using the following regression model.

$$PC = \alpha + \beta_1CSD + \beta_2DD + \beta_3ME + \epsilon \dots \dots \text{eq2}$$

Whereby;

PC = Performance of Census

α = Constant

ϵ = Error term

CSD = Collection of Socio-demographic Data

DDD = Data Development and Dissemination

ME = Monitoring and Evaluation

The results of linearity tests as per Table 1, show that the overall linear relationship between independent variables and the dependent variable was 0.01, more specifically CSD (r (209), > .386, $p < .000$), this shows that the correlation between ICT and population census

was positive and significant because the collection of socio-demographic data was found to have the p-value was less than 0.05. on the other hand, DDD ($r(209) > .627$, $p, < .000$), these results can be interpreted that data development and dissemination were also found to have a positive and significant relationship to

population census because the p-value was found to .000 level of significance which is less than 0.05. Lastly, ME ($r(207) > .193$, $p, < .005$), monitoring and evaluation were also found to have a positive and significant relationship, this means that the use of ICT in population census facilitates effective monitoring and evaluation.

Table 2 Linearity Test

Variable					
PC	Pearson (r)	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)				
	N	209			
CSD	Pearson (r)	.386**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000			
	N	209	209		
DD	Pearson (r)	.251**	.627**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		
	N	209	209	209	
ME	Pearson (r)	.605**	.390**	.193**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.005	
	N	209	209	209	209

Note: **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The model summary Table 4, summarizes the results obtained from four variables/predictors namely CSD (Collection of Social Demographic Data), DD (Development and Dissemination) and ME (Monitoring and Evaluation), while the dependent variables were PC (performance of Census). The value of R is .628 and $R^2 = .594$ adjusted to .586, the results can be interpreted as the factor for the prediction of the performance

of population census with the use of ICT systems. The overall performance of the ICT system is estimated at 62.8%. On the Durbin – Watson value was 2.134 which suggests that the residual was normally distributed. The value of Durbin – Watson is normally required to range between 0 – 4 to confirm the presence of autocorrelation.

Table 3 Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. error in the Estimate	Sig. F Change	Durbin-Watson
1	.628 ^a	.594	.586	1.003	.000	2.134

Table 4 ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	134.245	3	44.748	44.510	.000 ^b
	Residual	206.099	205	1.005		
	Total	340.344	208			

Anova Test was used to show the interaction of effects between variables within the group hence it helps to confirm further complex propositions

(Pallant, 2007). In this study, a one-way ANOVA was preferred to relate the mean value of the impact of ICT on the performance of the

census process in Tanzania. The factor loading showed the result of the F – Test which was 44.510 and confirmed the existing relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variables. The relationship was statistically significant at .000 as shown by Sig Values.

Table 4, the results of the use of the ICT system it's the collection of the socio-demographic information CSD ($\beta = .138, p < .001$), which means that the ICT system had a positive and significant relationship with the conduct of the population census. Also from the analysis, it was shown that Data Development and

Dissemination (DDD) was found to have ($\beta = .061, p < .003$), which means that there was a positive and significant relationship between ICTS systems and the conduct of population census since this system ensured effective data development and dissemination of the same after collection from different fields. The finding obtained about the Monitoring and Evaluation (ME) showed that there was ($\beta = .539, p < .000$) there was a positive and significant relationship between the use of ICT systems in the population census since the increase of ICT systems led to the effective monitoring and evaluation of the census process.

Table 5 Regression Coefficient

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.511	.643		2.352	.020
CSD	.178	.096	.138	1.848	.001
DDD	.146	.168	.061	.869	.003
ME	.870	.095	.539	9.112	.000

Table 6 Role of Effective Census Information on National Development Programs

S/N	Responses	1 F (%)	2 F (%)	3 F (%)	4 F (%)	5 F (%)
1	Census facilitate formulation of the National strategic plan	0	53(25.4)	42(20.1)	50(23.9)	64(30.6)
2	Population census is useful in resource distribution	13(6.2)	0	33(15.8)	67(32.1)	96(45.9)
3	It facilitates provision and accessibility of social services	0	13(6.2)	0	142(67.9)	54(25.8)
4	Census serves as basis for equitable representation	0	22(10.5)	42(20.1)	62(29.7)	83(39.7)
5	Census can help to facilitate the distribution of human capital	13(6.2)	42(20.1)	0	71(34.0)	83(39.7)
6	It provides suitable data base for comparison and projection of demographic data in certain period of time	16(7.7)	15(7.2)	0	109(52.2)	69(33.0)
7	Census information enable distribution of the national income	0	0	15(7.2)	101(48.3)	93(44.5)
8	The government can easily develop strategies for collection of revenues	13(6.2)	0	0	129(61.7)	67(32.1)

Table 6, results of this shows that 56% of the respondents agrees that census information facilitates formulation of the national strategic plan, 78% of the respondents who participated in this study agree that census information is

useful in facilitating resources distribution in the country. Also, 93.7% of the respondents who participated in this study agree that census information facilitates provision and accessibility of social services. Furthermore 69.4% of the

respondents agree that census information serves as basis for equitable representation. It shows that 73.7% of the respondents who participated in this study agree that census information can help to facilitate the distribution of human capital. Other 92.8% of the respondents who participated in this study agree that census information enable distribution of the national income, 93.8% of the respondents agrees that through census information government can easily develop strategies for collection of revenues.

Discussion

Findings obtained through regression analysis revealed that model summary revealed R of .628 which is equal to 62.8% which means that the use of the ICT system in the collection of demographic information has importance at about 62.8% but also the level of significance was .000 which means the there is a positive and significant relation between the application of ICT and the collection of the demographic information of the respondents as shown in Table 4.8. The results obtained through Anova Test depicted an F statistic of 44.510 with a p-value of .000 which shows that the ICT system positively and significantly affects the performance of the population census. More specifically the use of the ICT system it's the collection of the socio-demographic information CSD ($\beta = .138, p < .001$), which means that the ICT system had a positive and significant relationship with the conduct of the population census. Also from the analysis, it was shown that Data Development and Dissemination (DDD) was found to have ($\beta = .061, p < .003$), which means that there was a positive and significant relationship between ICT systems and the conduct of population census since these systems ensured effective data development and dissemination of the same after collection from different fields. The finding obtained about the Monitoring and Evaluation (ME) showed that there was ($\beta = .539, p < .000$).

The findings obtained revealed that even modest advancements in census technology may have significant impacts on the efficiency and efficacy

of the whole census process (Mahesh, 2019). The use of the ICT system has improved as compared to the manual system of data collection (Cantoni, & Danowski, 2015). ICT systems have become very significant in the entire process because it facilitates an easier way of collecting data while maintaining confidentiality as well as maintaining integrity (Creswell, 2003). In the same way, provided that the use of the ICT system has facilitated making simple and easy for the general population census (Feridun, 2019). Technology has been a cost-effective system in terms of resources and manpower (Grossman, 2019).

Thus, from the finding of this study the results obtained showed that census information has a role to play on the national development programs in Tanzania (Grossman, 2019). These established that in a number of countries, the population census plays a major role in the allocation of the government resources (Castano, 2018), it helps to determine the size of population the country has in order to forecast if the amount of money that is provided by the government for development efforts is sufficient (Jennifer, 2022). Also, suggests that census information is used in just about all planning decisions (Juan, 2017). The census of population provides information on the age and sex distribution, in addition to household composition and size all of which are vital in determining the needs of different segments of the population (Mahesh, 2019). The government in the world continues to undertake census due to the gain the countries stand to gain from such gigantic task (Waite, 2010). Census is the main source of population statistics in many countries in the world (Sharma, 2017). It is also seen as a social photography of certain condition expressible in a population of a country at a given moment (Sheard, 2018).

Conclusion

The results obtained from this study revealed that ICT had importance in several ways such as ensuring that data which are collected are well-centered and managed for further processes such as timely computation of data collected also

it was revealed that ICT has facilitated a high-level of privacy of data provider data since they could not be any possibilities of data leaking or mismanagement (UN, 2017). Moreover, ICT could help to facilitate the efficient compilation of data, and accurate reporting while ICT could be used for data supervision from different fields of censuses as well as the encouragement of an open system of data management. Moreover, census information has a role to play on the national development programs, since it facilitates the allocation of the government resources, it helps to determine the size of population the country has in order to forecast if the amount of money that is provided by the government for development efforts is sufficient (Weyant, 2022). Since there were some challenges encountered major barriers were lack of genuine software, inadequate computer knowledge, and low-speed processing hence the researcher recommends that the government as the primary stakeholder of the national development should improve more intensified ICT systems since the use of more appropriate technology would help to increase more efficiency and effectiveness of the data collection process. The findings obtained in this study also suggested that the ICT systems helped in the collection of socio-demographic information of people, the study recommends the provision of effective measures to ensure the security and privacy of the information collected so that it cannot be mismanaged and misappropriated. Having conducted the research study on the impacts of the ICT system in the performance of population census in Tanzania. The study recommends further research be conducted on the factors affecting the application of ICT systems in the population census in Tanzania. This study will create a comprehensive and general understanding of the challenges which can affect the performance of the ICT systems in undertaking the population census.

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